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Sociological Impact of Advertisements on Saudi Arabian Consumers

Mohammad Naquibur Rahman, Ph.D¹, Sabahat Naaz, MBA²

¹ Associate Professor of Marketing, College of Business, Umm Al Qura University, Makkah, Saudi Arabia

² Manager at Big Bazar, Patna, India, L.N.Mishra Institute of social science, Patna, India

Correspondence: Mohammad Naquibur Rahman. Email: uqu.naquib@gmail.com, mnahman@uqu.edu.sa

Abstract

The impact of advertisement can be seen very clearly in various ways on Saudi consumers in the Kingdom. The purpose of this article is to investigate the impact of modern advertisement on Saudi consumers and how it influences the purchase behavior of consumers. This research article outlines the challenges and given rise to the new business economic order giving a boost to the sale and purchase in the indigenous market as internet, and mobile facilities are available. Furthermore, this research paper highlighted that a new global culture with a new socio-economic setup has cropped up with set up of preference and options that could cater to global taste requirement and outlook.

Keywords: Impact of Advertisement, Consumer Buying Behavior, Saudi Consumers, Consumer Awareness

1. Introduction

Saudi Arabia is very important from geo-political aspect amongst Gulf Countries, and its oil strength had Saudi Arabian known the art of interdependence, the history would have been different altogether. It has great strength to play the role of impact in the region. Presently Saudi Arabia is one of the largest advertising markets in the gulf region, accounting for 40 % of all advertising costs in the Gulf region. The Saudi Arabia market account is, however meager but per capital expenditure is very significant. It is important to mention here that the prime targets of the best international advertising firms. Print media assumes the most important part of advertising expenditures in the Kingdom, of Saudi Arabia with newspapers accounting for 61% of the spending, magazines 23% and television just 16%.

Ministry of Commerce of KSA government¹ claimed that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is the largest duty free market in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), where it has 25% of the total regional GDP (Gross Domestic

¹ <https://mci.gov.sa/en/AboutKingdom/Pages/SaudiEconomy.aspx>

Product), partially, because of the geographical location that helps it easily access export and import markets in Europe, Asia, and Africa.

The sociological impact of advertisement is to make the consumer aware of social, economic behavioral change taking the place of every level of time. It makes him aware of the new outlook of modern advertisement needed to cater to information with the new socio-economic growth of modern advertisement. The social perspective of modern advertisement basically informs buyers and consumers from the Saudi consumer standpoint of the welfare of the society as a whole in which consumer is seen from the social aspect. The growth of modern advertisement without the social perspective would be incomplete as the point of view of consumers as an individual is also must with the growth of modern advertisement in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia. It has become more dynamic and multidimensional the social and economic growth of modern advertisement is to highlight the socio-economic change taking place in modern business world. Firstly it create awareness of the new social change, the commercial, cultural and all interchange of the techniques as well as global events taking place in the modern business world. The social and economic aspects of modern advertisement are to inform the consumers to the socio-economic values basically. Replacing the former and conventional economic policies and also make them aware that competence and survival of the society can be kept alive taking into account the new socio-economic values, system, techniques not only indigenous but also on the global plane.

There are various roles of advertisements basically is to inform, educate, and create an awareness are a know-how with consumers. So that they may have many options about selection and rejection of the consumer goods with new social change, a new vision of sale, and purchase system. Advertisement furnishes information with new market strategies and their needs e.g., satisfaction, economy, etc. The role of advertisement is to inform consumers about their products, prices, and places where the products are available. It also helps marketers achieve their objectives, and all variable must work together to achieve advertising objectives. Furthermore, the role of advertisements is to inform buyer the qualitative and inner worth and outward glamour of finished consumer products, so that they fall into pitfalls of an impulse purchase. The role of advertising in a society has been a great topic of a good debate. Advertising may be useful for consumers in order to enhance awareness from the customer standpoint of view of dissemination of information. Such information is necessary when buyers have to make a choice from the various products and services or from a variety of products. It can be argued that the advertising in Saudi Arabia is gradually gaining in sophistication and importance due to the increase in sales volume, sales promotions different kind of merchandising schemes which has risen considerably in last decade. Therefore, it gives updated information to consumers with every social change in new modern socio-economic world.

2. Literature Review

After the post liberalized economy, the success of the business depends upon the business environment and a wide knowledge of the consumers. Knowledge of consumers starts by cognitive approach. According to (Abideen & Saleem, 2011), "television and internet advertisements are the best mode of advertisement to attract targeted customers in a high competitive market. Television Advertisement can be defined as "any paid form of non-personal communication of ideas or products on the electronic media to end-user" (Bogdanovic, 2013). Buying Attitude has been defined as an inside self-general evaluation of any entity such as; people, objects, advertisements, or issues (Solomon, 2013). (Tai, 2007). According to Alwitt & Prabhaker (1992, 1994), people show an encouraging approach toward advertising. Such attitudes toward advertising were discovered to be affected by demographic variables. Many studies s showed that if there are favorable attitudes toward advertising, attitudes toward both specific type of advertising and products purchase intention will be influenced (MacKenzie et al., 1986; Shavitt, et al., 1998). Furthermore, consumer buying behavior towards advertising was found to be partially mediated by attitudes toward product placements in games on respondents' perceived purchasing behaviors (Nelson et al., 2010). Wijesundara C.B. Galdolage B.S². (2007) claimed that researchers found out that there is a moderate positive relationship of TV ads viewing of children and the bad food habits. It makes a substantial contribution to childhood obesity, because commercials promote unhealthy dietary practices. Most food advertisements are high-calorie foods –such as fast foods, sweetened foods, cereals, etc. TV viewing has also

² https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280098783_IMPACT_OF_TV_ADVERTISING_ON_CHILDREN'S_BEHAVIOR

caused childhood obesity as not doing any exercise during that time. Rafique³ et al., 2012 claimed that advertisement is a way to communicate with the audience. Thus if we say that advertisement is like magic than it will not be false because advertisement actually changes the needs and wants of the people and sometimes it creates the need among the people. People are highly affected by the advertisements, and organizations are trying to target the masses.

According to Rai,⁴ 2013, there are several national and international brands which consumers recognized and have a strong perception in their minds. These perceptions are pinched in their mind because of their culture, lifestyles, and surroundings. Also, advertisements have a very important role in shaping the consumer mind and behavior. Advertisements are the source of motivation which forces them to buy a particular product. Furthermore, it can be said that the advertisements are also a source of building trust and brand loyalty.

Samar Fatima et al., mentioned (2015) Consumers in all over the world are attracted towards the brand and products which are emotionally attached with their behaviors. Studies found that emotional attachments put a huge influence on the customers and their buying behavior as people tend to associate themselves with the brand.⁵

After reviewing the literature, we come up with the idea that intense work has been done on the television advertisement impact on consumer buying behavior, but little work as per our research has been seen on impact of religiosity on the relationship between television advertisement and consumer buying behavior, so we have chosen this research topic. It can be said that television advertising is still the most pervasive and powerful tool for reaching Saudi Arabian consumers. For small businesses, however, the barriers to using TV ads can be daunting; airtime can be very expensive, and good commercials are difficult and costly to create. The Internet may grab all of the attention these days, but TV is still the media king. According to one recent study, the average American spends more than four and a half hours a day in front of the tube — and a whopping 99 percent of all U.S. households have at least one TV. Therefore, advertising has played a very important role in developing brand name, credibility, and product awareness which will help in consumers buying decision (Bovee & Arens, 1992; Eze & Lee, 2012). Rahman Mohammad Naquibur (2015) has considerably mentioned in his research paper⁶ Here is a tremendous impact of the emergence of Saudi society by virtue of which incoming global factors. As a result of which internet, online retailing and other moderns system and techniques of communication have become popular in the middle east and KSA.

Advertisements generally have an influence on how we perceive things around us. Through various types of advertisements, especially TVCs, portray how a user of a certain product is or should be. It sometimes shows the social class the user of a product belong to, their lifestyle and attitudes. In cases of beauty product, this concept is highly applicable. In a research conducted in 2009, it was observed that one of the most influential ideas spread by the media is society's perception of beauty and attractiveness. The thin, beautiful woman and the handsome muscular men are seen everywhere. As the influence of media increases, the pressure to hold on to these ideals increases (Russello, 2009). YWCA USA published a report, Beauty at Any Cost, which emphasized the concerns of the beauty obsession on women and girls in America through social media in 2009⁷. According to this report, the ceaseless pursuit of perfection is more toxic to American women and girls than ever. This feeling of insecurity and obsession is very much likely to trigger the purchase of beauty products (Britton, 2012).

3. Research Objectives

In day to day business companies spend huge money on advertising of their products and children, and they believe advertising aimed at children have a great influence on consumer behavior. The literature and some of the eminent

³ <http://www.ijmtbr.com/PDF/IJMTBR-2019-07-03-10.pdf>

⁴ Rai, N. (2013). IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR AND ATTITUDE WITH REFERENCE TO CONSUMER DURABLES. International journal of management research and business strategy ISSN 2319-345X Vol. 2, No. 2.

⁵ Samar Fatima and samreen Lodhi Impact of Advertisement on Buying Behaviours of the consumers: Study of Cosmetic industry of Karachi International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research, Oct-2015 ISSN (2226-8235) Vol-4, Issue 10

⁶ Organized Retailing in Context with Amalgamation of Small Firms in Saudi Arabia 2015 International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences 2015; 3(5): 583-593 ISSN: 2326-9553 (Print); ISSN: 2326-9561 (Online)

⁷ <https://www.latimes.com/style/la-igw-ywca19-2008aug19-story.html>

authors reveal that there is a positive impact on Saudi consumers and also their involvement in buying decision process of commodities with the influence of advertisement.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the following objectives:

1. To find out whether children targeted TV advertisements influence the buying
2. To find out the impact of advertising on the consumer on their own selection in purchasing decision of product and services
3. To find out the sociological impact of advertisements on consumers
4. To find out the consumers are getting advertising heroes as a role model
5. To find out the consumers targeted advertisements influence the consumptions of targeted products.

4. Methodology

The design of the proposed research is descriptive, which is used for describing people who take part in the study, primarily for gaining insights and ideas about the research problem and the variables and issues associated with those problems. For the survey purpose, the questionnaire was developed to collect primary data, and secondary data is collected using a journal, books, and the internet.

4.1. Data Collection

Primary Data is collected from respondents through observation and survey. To conduct surveys, questionnaire has been used as it is a quick source of information. Therefore, data collection for the present study was collected from graduate students (Male & Female) of the western and southern region of Saudi Arabia. The students participated in the study in the presence of the professors, and in each class, questionnaire were distributed to graduate students.

The Secondary Data has been collected using different books, journals, reports, articles, and periodicals, including the World Wide Web.

Respondents for the survey were selected by non-probability –convenience method in accordance with the judgment of the researchers and 200 consumers age group of 18-40 including male-female from Makkah Jeddah and Jizan of the Western and southern province of Saudi Arabia. All respondents were those with much exposure to the television, and this sample size is also enough to generalize findings in context to Sociological impact of advertising on Saudi consumers.

4.2. Tools

The present research work is to find out the impact of advertisement on the Saudi consumers. The developed Questionnaire is based on the 5point Likert scale with some open-ended questions. It is separated into three sections. A first section describes the consumer profile. The Second section is constructed on the variables used to analyze the decision of consumers. In 5 point Likert scale, the 1 is used as "strongly disagree," and 5 as "strongly agree." The Third section, based on open-ended questions, to get a more flexible view. To avoid any ambiguity due consideration was undertaken.

4.3 Data Analysis

From total of 200 respondents, there were 150 male and 50 female from three different cities Makkah Jeddah and Jizan. Their percentage was 75 % & 25 % respectively, and their age group in between 18-24 and all are under grade students of different colleges. Most of them are Management or marketing students. As mentioned in table 1

Table 1: Respondents from each city of targeted consumers

	Male	Female	Total
Makkah	49	22	71
Jeddah	60	18	78
Jizan	41	10	51
Total	150	50	200

Table 2: Respondents spending time on watching advertisement

Exposure of TV Ads Per Day	Overall	Male Respondent	Female Respondent
Single Time	12.4	14.1	11.6
Two Times	30.5	30.5	32.6
Three Times	15.0	15.9	13.7
And more	39.7	37.9	42.1

Table 3 summarizes the Saudi consumers like to watch different kinds of advertisement through Television, the internet, and social media. It is observed that entertaining advertisement most liked by 78 percent of the respondent. 61 percent respondent influenced by celebrities involved in a consumer products advertisement. 35 percent of respondent they like advertisement on social issues in order to aware the society.

Table 3: Types of Advertisement

Advertisement	Overall %	Male respondent %	Female respondent %
Entertainments	78.1	69.6	86.5
Beverages Products	61	58	65
Detergent	52	34	75
Cosmetics	40	35.2	48.1
Environment	35	41	31
Food products	42	31	54
Electronics	47	73	13

Our research was based on cross sectional data of 15 questions. With 5 independent variables, (Need have 6 questions), (Entertainment have 3 questions), (Dominance have 2 questions), (Brand Recall have 4 questions) and (Stimulation have 3 questions). We have given simple descriptive statistics of independent variables in Table 4.

Table 4: Impact of Advertisement with reference to need

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Does advertisement influence to customers	3	16	27	125	29
Do you like print media, social media or electronic media	3	9	12	151	25
Does outdoor displays of advertisements are helpful in your day to day life	9	19	35	122	15
Do you think to survive in highly competitive market advertisement is must	4	26	35	127	8
Do you purchase the product and service when you feel it's highly needed	3	9	23	145	20
Does advertisement attractive to your needs	6	15	31	120	28
Do you purchase the product and service when you feel it's highly needed	3	9	23	145	20

As above mentioned table revealed that the 62.5 % consumers agree & 14.5 % strongly agrees that advertisement is necessary to catch the consumer's attraction. In the second question, 60% of consumers agree, and 15.5 % are neutral that helpful print media ads to be necessary. In next 54.54% are agree and 16% are neutral that street ads are relevant to daily life. In the fourth question, 61% agrees that street ads are poorly displayed. In fifth, 61.47% of consumers are agree that in this competitive market any product can't survive without advertisement. In the last question, 72.5% of consumers agree that they buy goods when they feel it is necessary.

Table 5: Impact of advertisement on consumer purchase behavior

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Does advertisement always influence consumer purchase behavior	7	6	18	149	20
Does global advertising enhancing your style of living	3	6	19	135	37

In table no 5 the first question, 75.62% of consumers agree that advertisement always having an influence of the silver screen. Next question 67% of consumers agree that they purchase some of the items to satisfy their needs, including enhancing the stranded living and style in modern society.

Table 6: Impact of Advertisement with reference to brand image

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Does advertisement create the awareness, about the products	7	20	5	140	27
Does advertisement persuade you to buy the advertise products	11	21	18	130	20
Does global advertisement create the brand image about a particular products	3	9	22	112	14
Does your purchase habits influenced by reference group family friends and a social group	13	28	34	152	14
Does advertisement motivate you to switch from one product to other products	12	21	32	148	12
Does advertisement always encourage you on your purchase behavior	3	17	5	151	24
Does advertisement have any negative impact on our social behavior	12	13	24	120	25

With reference to the table, No 6 question ten shows that 80 consumers agree and 33 consumers strongly agree that advertisement is a key source of awareness about the products. Next 65 % are agreeing that advertisement persuaded to buy the products and services. In question number twelve, 58.87% agrees that the consumer influenced by advertisement and create a brand image about their products. With reference 13 question 76% consumes are agree that their purchase habits influenced by reference group, family friends, and majorly from the social group. Finally, with reference to the last question, 60 % of consumers accepted that there is a negative aspect feel with human relationship.

6. Discussion

It is worth mentioning that the data mentioned in this dissertation has been gathered from 200 respondents of leading cities like Jeddah, Makah, and Jizan by virtue of a self-structured questionnaire. What is important to mention is that stratified random sampling has been applied. The finding of this research paper is as follows and taking into account of methodology and applied on a variable the following:

The result of the present research study shows that there are positive and significant impacts of an advertisement on Saudi consumers. Generally, television advertisements create awareness, knowledge, interest, and purchase decision about a particular product and services. These impacts also lead to influence the buying behavior of the consumer and build the behaviors of society regarding product and services.

85% of consumers get involved and influenced with an advertisement when purchasing goods or services, but 68% of the purchasing goods for them, but 68% of consumers between age 18-25 they pick and choose, liking and options and matching their needs with the advertisements.

Advertisements on different channels in Saudi Arabia like Bahrain, Qatar, and Dubai based Indian channels are taken into consideration in this study to see the sociological impact of advertisement on Saudi consumers. To know and understand the real exposure of an advertisement on Saudi consumers and they were asked to know that on an average per day how many times the watched television and social media advertisements during in the break time of different programs.

The impact of advertisement on Saudi consumers, women, children were found a deep craze the adopting the sophisticated ways of living made an impact on their being giving way to the new scale of socio-economic socio-cultural values. At the same time in brings, emphasis on attitude, preferences and behavioral changes previously in the modern post liberalized economy is important, in result a new socio-economic phenomena, awareness and conscious have influenced the Saudi Arabian consumers. The KSA has a large number of number of middle-class consumers, which gives a boost to sales& purchased and steady growth to the GDP also. Therefore, socioeconomic factors play an important role in enhancing the impact of advertisement, and it can be seen in a different way of life Saudi Arabian context. As a matter of fact, that advertisement creates awareness, knowledge, options preferences, and reaction about and advertised products. It also influences the Purchase decision of Saudi consumers. In addition, it can be said that the advertisement helps the consumers to choose or select their right product to satisfy needs or want.

The present research paper also reflects how Saudi Arabian consumers, teenagers, students, housewives have gone a state of dilemma or they are feeling in an embrace situation after made interacted with a global, western advertisement on the silver screen, at the same time Saudi consumers conscious about the modern advertisement. The present research paper the impact of advertisement on Saudi consumers also put emphasis on how to preserve the indigenes market, and it is equally important with every social or environmental change. At the same time, a significant change has started taking place in socio-cultural normative pattern of Saudi Arabia.

7. Conclusion

In the post liberalized economy the sociological impact of advertisement can be seen very clearly:

1. Awareness of variety of consumer goods that bring them near satisfaction or need or requirement in the Saudi Arabian society, by education and training of Saudi consumers that create a decision-making power to opt and select right choice of consumer products keeping in view of cultural heritage or in the Saudi Arabian perspective.
2. Impact of advertisement exposes the consumers to the global culture, values, and consumer goods finding into the market.
3. In order to make consumer awareness from fallacious slogans flashed on silver screen, radio magazines and internet to prevent from the impulse purchase of consumer products.

4. A conflict can be seen very clearly in between the indigenes value and global value similarly regional culture and global culture as a result shift in morality e.g. cigarette smoking drink and sex appealing pictures.
5. An another conflict take place in between Saudi companies and multinational companies as a result the inflow of multinational companies gave a rise to amalgamation of indigenes in result a large number of indigenes companies took over by multinational companies like Riyad laben, Western Bakeries, Hadco, IBS (International Baking Services) taken over by Al Marai company, Geant hypermarket, Gaint Supermarket taken over by Hyper Panda, Al-Aujan soft drink company taken over Coca Cola KSA company. Therefore, there is decline in revenues and goodwill of to the traditional products as well as traditional markets also.
6. Sociological impact of advertisement has been given rise to the new economic order and giving boost to sale and purchase in indigenes market.

This is not least but last a new global culture with a new socio economic setup has cropped up with set of preferences and options that could cater to global taste requirement and outlook

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